

Illustrated Technical Paper - Enhanced Pub/Sub Network Communication

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Abstract

This "ILLUSTRATED TECHNICAL PAPER" presents the slides describing the contents of the paper "Enhanced Pub/Sub Communications for Massive IoT Traffic with SARSA Reinforcement Learning".

The talk was presented at the **3rd International Conference on Machine Learning for Networking (MLN'2020)**, 24 - 26 November 2020 at Paris, France (<http://www.adda-association.org/mln-2020/>).

The "illustrated technical paper format" is intended to complement, enrich and subsidize the technical paper content and contains slides, complementary text and additional and/or focused bibliographic references.

Index Terms

Publish/ Subscribe, Reinforcement Learning, SARSA, IoT, Massive IoT Traffic, Resource Allocation, Network Communications.

1 PAPER ABSTRACT [1]

Sensors are being extensively deployed and are expected to expand at significant rates in the coming years. They typically generate a large volume of data on the internet of things (IoT) application areas like smart cities, intelligent traffic systems, smart grid, and e-health. Cloud, edge and fog computing are potential and competitive strategies for collecting, processing, and distributing IoT data. However, cloud, edge, and fog-based solutions need to tackle the distribution of a high volume of IoT data efficiently through constrained and limited resource network infrastructures. This paper addresses the issue of conveying a massive volume of IoT data through a network with limited communications resources (bandwidth) using a cognitive communications resource allocation based on Reinforcement Learning (RL) with SARSA algorithm. The proposed network infrastructure (PSIoTRL) uses a Publish/ Subscribe architecture to access massive and highly distributed IoT data. It is demonstrated that the PSIoTRL bandwidth allocation for buffer flushing based on SARSA enhances the IoT aggregator buffer occupation and network link utilization. The PSIoTRL dynamically adapts the IoT aggregator traffic flushing according to the Pub/Sub topic's priority and network constraint requirements.

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2 PAPER SLIDES

Enhanced Pub/Sub Communications for Massive IoT Traffic with SARSA Reinforcement Learning

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05/01/2021

1

Fig. 1.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

This work addresses the issue of enhancing the utilization of a communication channel (MPLS label switched path - LSP, physical link, fiber optics slot, others) deployed in network infrastructures with limited resources (bandwidth) using the SARSA reinforcement learning algorithm. The target application area is the massive exchange of IoT data using the Pub/Sub paradigm. The framework integrating the SARSA module with the Pub/Sub message exchange deployment (PSIoT described in [2]) is the PSIoTRL.

-- > Paper to read:

- The full paper text describing the PSIoTRL is "**Enhanced Pub/Sub Communications for Massive IoT Traffic with SARSA Reinforcement Learning**" [1] and is available at:

- * DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4413404>
- * ARXIV: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2101.00687.pdf>
- * ZENODO: https://zenodo.org/record/4413404#.X_TijNhKjIU
- * Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348169267_Enhanced_PubSub_Communications_for_Massive_IoT_Traffic_with_SARSA_Reinforcement_Learning

-- > Complementary papers describing Pub/Sub and communication requirements on Smart Cities and other application scenarios are available at:

- Smart City and communications requirements and solutions: [3] [4] [5] [6] [7]

Paper Target - Summary

Fig. 2.

— > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

The PSIoTRL general view and basic components.

This work addresses the issue of enhancing the utilization of a communication channel (MPLS label switched path - LSP, physical link, fiber optics slot, others) deployed in network infrastructures with limited resources (bandwidth) using the SARSA reinforcement learning algorithm. The target application area is the massive exchange of IoT data using the Pub/Sub paradigm. The framework integrating the SARSA module with the Pub/Sub message exchange deployment (PSIoT described in [2]) is the PSIoTRL.

Current scenario

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Fig. 3.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

Sensors are being extensively deployed and are expected to expand at significant rates in the coming years in the internet of things (IoT) application areas like smart city, intelligent traffic systems (ITS), connected and autonomous vehicles (CAV), video analytics in public safety (VAPS) and mobile e-health [8] [9], to mention some.

Cloud, edge and fog computing are currently the most prevailing and competing used strategies to convey IoT data between producers and consumers. They use several different alternatives to decide where to process, how to distribute, and where to store IoT data [10]. Nevertheless, cloud, edge, and fog-based solutions need to tackle the distribution of a high volume of IoT data efficiently.

IoT data distribution, whatever data handling, processing, or storing strategy used, does require efficient network communications infrastructures. In fact, there is a research challenge on enhancing network communications and providing efficient resource allocation based on the fact that, in many applications like IoT, networks have limited and constrained resources [11].

Machine learning and reinforcement learning with distinct algorithms like Q-Learning [12], deep reinforcement learning [13], and SARSA (State-Action-Reward-State-Action) [14] are being applied to support an efficient allocation of resources in networks for application areas like 5G, cognitive radio, and mobile edge computing, to mention some [15] [16].

The Publish/Subscribe (Pub/Sub) paradigm is extensively used as an enabler for data distribution in various scenarios like information-centric networking, data-centric systems, smart grid, and other general group-based communications [17] [18] [19]. The Pub/Sub paradigm is an alternative for IoT data distribution between producers and consumers in general [18] [2].

Objective and Contributions

- This paper addresses the issue of **enhancing the transport of a massive volume of IoT data** through a network with limited communications resources (bandwidth).
- The **PSIoTRL solution** is a cognitive **communications resource allocation** based on **Reinforcement Learning (RL)** with SARSA algorithm
- **PSIoTRL** uses **Pub/ Sub** to access and transfer massive and highly distributed IoT data

The **contribution** is **multi-fold**:

- **Modeling the SARSA agent** with a generic buffer occupation metric achieving a **limited amount of SARSA states** and not using extensive computational resources
- To demonstrate **the enhancement of Pub/Sub communications** with SARSA by dynamically adjusting IoT aggregators queues occupation to Pub/Sub topics priority and network resources availability

Fig. 4.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

Differently from other proposals for network infrastructure resource allocation and optimization that consider, for instance, the quality of service for the entire set of network nodes and Pub/Sub aggregators, the SARSA-based PSIoTRL framework provides a simple data ingress based solution. In fact, it controls the quality of Pub/Sub topics data distribution in an aggregator by keeping Pub/Sub buffer topics occupation below a defined threshold. This indirectly means that a certain amount of bandwidth is available for the Pub/Sub topic and, consequently, a level of quality is allocated for the communication channel. Since the Pub/Sub data transfers are dynamically requested, SARSA deploys a dynamic control of bandwidth allocation for buffer data flushing.

The contribution of this work is multi-fold. Firstly, we modeled the SARSA agent communications with a generic buffer occupation metric. The adopted metric results in a limited amount of SARSA states to allow the allocation of bandwidth preserving Pub/Sub topic priorities without using extensive computational resources. Moreover, we demonstrate that Pub/Sub communications with SARSA can be enhanced by dynamically adjusting IoT aggregators queues occupation to Pub/Sub topics priority and network resources availability.

Fig. 5.

- **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
Related Work:

Architectural and system-wide studies about IoT massive data processing and data flow in smart cities are presented in Al-Fuqaha [20], Rathore [21] and Martins [22]. Al-Fuqaha [20] introduces the concept of cognitive smart city where IoT and artificial intelligence are merged in a three-level model with different requirements. In relation to the communication level, the basic approach assumes a fog cloud computing (fog-CC) communication without considering any specific IoT massive traffic requirement. In fact, the proposal assumes that the aggregation with edge processing reduces the required bandwidth for fog-CC communication to a minimum. Rathore [21] explores the issue of big data analytics for smart cities. The paper proposes an edge-based aggregation and processing strategy for raw data. Processed data is forwarded through gateways to smart city applications using Internet and assuming bandwidth reduction at edge-level. Martins [22] discusses the potential benefits and impacts of how some technological enablers, like software-defined networking [23] and machine learning [24], are integrated and aim at cognitive management [16]. IoT data edge-processed aggregation, network communication and service deployments towards an efficient overall smart city solution are discussed and the relevance of intelligent communication resource provisioning and deployment are highlighted.

Machine learning in communication networks is broadly addressed by Cote [15] and Boutaba et al in [11].

Intelligent network communication resources are considered by Zhao [25]. The work presents a smart routing solution for crowdsourcing data with mobile edge computing (MEC) in smart cities using reinforcement learning (RL). The solution defines routes, differently from ours that optimizes the bandwidth allocated for IoT flow flushing.

Reinforcement Learning

- ✓ Reinforcement learning (RL) is a largely used machine learning (ML) technique in which a trial-and-error learning process is executed by an agent that acts on a system aiming to maximize its rewards.
- ✓ SARSA (State-Action-Reward-State-Action) algorithm is the reinforcement learning approach used by PSioTRL framework.

Fig. 6.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a largely used machine learning (ML) technique in which a trial-and-error learning process is executed by an agent that acts on a system aiming to maximize its rewards. The RL algorithm is expected to learn how to reach or approach a certain objective by interacting with a system through a feedback loop [26] [12] [27].

The *value function* in RL is a prediction of the return available from each state, as indicated in Equation 1.

$$V(x_t) \leftarrow E\left\{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k}\right\} \quad (1)$$

Where r_t is the reward received for the transition from state x_t to x_{t+1} and γ is the discount factor ($0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$). The value function $V(x_t)$ represents the discounted sum of rewards received from step t onward. Therefore, it will depend on the sequence of actions taken and on the policy adopted to take these actions.

SARSA Algorithm

Features and potential advantages within the PSIoTRL framework include:

Being an on-policy algorithm, SARSA attempts to evaluate or improve the policy that is used to make decision;

SARSA avoids the state explosion issue common with the Q-learning algorithm;

PSIoTRL SARSA model uses a reduced state space and, consequently, SARSA behaves effectively by exploring all states at least once; and

Key issues that RL algorithms experience like bad initial performance and large training time are minimized in the PSIoTRL environment since SARSA addresses the allocation of network bandwidth locally with a reduced state-space.

Fig. 7.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

SARSA (State-Action-Reward-State-Action) algorithm is the reinforcement learning approach used by PSIoTRL framework [28] [14].

SARSA is a temporal-difference (TD) on-policy algorithm that learns the Q-values based on the action performed by the current policy. SARSA algorithm differs from Q-learning by the way it sets up the future reward. In SARSA the agent uses the action and the state at time $t + 1$ to update the Q-value. The SARSA tuple of main elements involved in the interaction process are:

$$\langle x_t, a_t, r_{t+1}, x_{t+1}, a_{t+1} \rangle \quad (2)$$

Where:

- x_t, a_t are the current state and action;
- r_{t+1} is the reward; and
- x_{t+1}, a_{t+1} are the next state and action reached using the policy ($\epsilon - Greedy$).

SARSA Q-values are therefore updated based on the Equations 3 or 4.

$$Q(x_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(x_t, a_t) + \alpha[r_{t+1} + \gamma Q(x_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - Q(x_t, a_t)] \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Q(x_{t-1}, a_{t-1}) = \alpha(t)[r_{t-1} + \gamma Q(x_t, a_t) - Q(x_{t-1}, a_{t-1})] \quad (4)$$

Where:

- α is the learning rate ($0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$); and
- γ is the discount factor ($0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$).

Fig. 8.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

Reinforcement learning with SARSA has proved efficient and obtained substantial success in resource allocation [14] [29], cloud computing [30] and computational offloading [31] [32].

An evaluation of SARSA and various other model-free algorithms is presented in Dafazio [33]. The evaluation considered diverse and difficult problems within a consistent environment (Arcade [34]) involving configuration aspects like Epsilon-greedy policy, exploration versus exploitation and state space with SARSA outperforming algorithms like Q-learning, ETTR (Expected Time-to-Rendezvous) [35], R-learning [36], GQ algorithm [37] and Actor-Critic algorithm [38].

SARSA algorithm features and potential advantages within the PSIoTRL environment include:

- Being an on-policy algorithm, SARSA attempts to evaluate or improve the policy that is used to make decision;
- SARSA avoids the state explosion issue common with the Q-learning algorithm;
- PSIoTRL has a reduced state space and, consequently, SARSA behaves effectively by exploring all states at least once; and
- Key issues that RL algorithms experience like bad initial performance and large training time are minimized in the PSIoTRL environment since SARSA addresses the allocation of network bandwidth locally with a reduced state-space.

- P. F. Moraes, R. F. Reale, and J. S. B. Martins, "A Publish/Subscribe QoS-aware Framework for Massive IoT Traffic Orchestration", in *Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on ADVANCEs in ICT Infrastructures and Services (ADVANCE)*, Santiago, Chile, jan. 2018, p. 1–14.
- P. F. Moraes, and J. S. B. Martins, "A Pub/Sub SDN-Integrated Framework for IoT Traffic Orchestration", in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems*, Paris, France, 2019, p. 11:1–11:9.

PSIoT Framework Functional View

- ✓ The PSIoT framework was designed to orchestrate massive IoT traffic and allocate network resources between producers and consumers.
- ✓ The PSIoT framework can schedule the data flow, based on Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, and allocates bandwidth on a backbone with limited resources.
- ✓ The PSIoT was modeled to operate with four main components: producers, consumers, a backbone with limited resources; and the orchestrator.
- ✓ The exchange of information is performed using the Pub/Sub architecture, whose characteristic of asynchronous, use of topics and the use of a broker, makes it attractive for IoT applications.

Fig. 9.

— > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

The objective of this work is to enhance the Publish/Subscribe (Pub/Sub) communications used in the context of massive IoT data transfers (Figure 9).

The Pub/Sub communications is supported by the PSIoT framework described in [2]. The PSIoT framework aims to efficiently handle network resources and IoT QoS requirements over the network between the IoT devices and consumer IoT applications [2]. Consumers are applications executed in servers located beyond the backbone network, cloud computing infrastructure accessed by the network or any other scheme that makes use of the managed network infrastructure for communications.

IoT data generated from sensors and devices can be aggregated and processed in the cloud or at the network edge, where each of these points are considered as *Aggregators* or *Producers* in the PSIoT framework. Whereas each client that receives IoT data, both end-users applications and even other aggregation nodes, are denoted as *Consumers*.

The PSIoT framework was designed to orchestrate massive IoT traffic and allocate network resources between producers and consumers. Besides, the PSIoT framework can schedule the data flow, based on Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, and allocates bandwidth on a backbone with limited resources. For this, the PSIoT was modeled to operate with four main components: producers, consumers, a backbone with limited resources; and the orchestrator [2].

PSIoT Pub/Sub Message Model

- ✓ PSIoT implements priority-based QoS levels when forwarding the data gathered by the aggregator queues to consumers:
- ❖ b0 (priority topic) – topics requiring high transmission rates and low delay;
- ❖ b1 (sensitive topic) – topics requiring reduced transmission rate and supporting larger delays; and
- ❖ b2 (insensitive topic) – topics whose requirements are manageable by best effort transmission.

Fig. 10.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

Aggregators are elements that gather the data obtained by connected sensors to send them (in an opportune moment) to their consumers (clients) using a Pub/Sub-style communication channel. In the opposite direction, aggregators deliver data received from producers to send them to actuators.

The exchange of information is performed through the Pub/Sub architecture, whose characteristic of asynchronous, use of topics and the use of a broker, makes it attractive for IoT applications [18].

PSIoT implements QoS when forwarding the data gathered by the aggregator to output buffers, according to the following characteristics [2]:

- b0 (priority) - high transmission rates and low delay application requirements for health care and data from critical industrial sensors, as examples;
- b1 (sensitive) - commercial data and security sensors; and
- b2 (insensitive) - best effort.

Fig. 12.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:

PSIoT Aggregator Configuration

- Consumers request IoT data on the aggregator's queues
- The aggregator empties its buffers according to consumer requests
- The aggregator queues are deployed with the following configuration:

Three IoT data queues (buffers) are configured per aggregator (one Pub/Sub topic per queue): B1, B2 and B3;

Initial buffer transmission rates are: T1, T2 and T3; and

Buffer priorities are: p1, p2 and p3 with p1 > p2 > p3.

Fig. 14.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

The PSIoT framework uses the Pub/Sub paradigm to produce and consume data. Consumers request IoT data on the aggregator's queues, and the aggregator empties its buffers according to consumer requests. The aggregator queues are deployed with the following configuration:

- Three IoT data queues (buffers) are configured per aggregator (one Pub/Sub topic per queue): B1, B2 and B3;
- Initial buffer transmission rates¹ are: T1, T2 and T3; and
- Buffer priorities are: p1, p2 and p3 with p1 > p2 > p3.

For this evaluation we consider one aggregator Ag_i located at network node n_z that delivers IoT data to a set of consumers C_i , with $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ located at network node n_y . Between nodes n_z and n_y there is a communication resource (MPLS LSP, physical link, fiber slot, other) with a limited bandwidth BW_{nz} . The communication resource interconnecting Pub/Sub producer and consumers is then constrained as follows:

$$BW_{zy} \geq \sum_{j=1}^n TB_j \tag{5}$$

Where TB_j is the currently transmission rate to empty a buffer j .

The aggregator monitors buffer occupation and occupation above a defined threshold limit is signaled to the orchestrator (Figure 14).

1. By initial buffer transmission rate, we mean the configured initial transmission rate to empty buffers without any buffer over-utilization.

Fig. 15.

— > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

The PSIoTRL SARSA agent is modeled with a finite set of states for the aggregator output queues, a finite set of configuration actions to be executed on each queue, and a set of reward values for each state/action transition pair.

In the SARSA agent, the system state S_i represents the overall aggregator’s output queue status in terms of occupation at a given time t_i .

The SARSA agent states are indicated in Figure 15. Each queue has two states either below (BL) or above (AL), a preconfigured threshold. Having two states for each queue allows, in this context, sufficient information for bandwidth allocation and contributes to avoid the common state explosion issue existing in many RL deployments.

The PSIoTRL SARSA agent actions are illustrated in Figure 15. Three actions are defined for each buffer: increase capacity (transmission rate), reduce capacity (transmission rate) and do nothing. Therefore, twenty seven actions are possible for each agent state. The amount of bandwidth increased or reduced per queue is a SARSA configuration parameter. A set of rewards is also defined for each executed state/action pair.

The SARSA ϵ -Greedy Policy

- ✓ The SARSA agent uses an ϵ -greedy policy since it must exploit as much as possible the acquired knowledge but also explores new possibilities of enhancing the allocation of bandwidth for queue communications.
- ✓ The ϵ -greedy policy matches adequately the inherent need of a Pub/Sub IoT message delivery framework where:
 - ✓ Random demands from consumers request Pub/Sub data with different priorities.
 - ✓ These demands generate a random volume of data to be transferred (aggregator to consumers).
- ✓ The per-queue bandwidth allocation must be dynamically computed among IoT data queues considering the existing constraint (bandwidth limitation) of the available communication channel.
- ✓ No value change or on-the-fly fine-tuning of ϵ was considered.

Fig. 16.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

The SARSA agent uses an ϵ -greedy policy since it must exploit as much as possible the acquired knowledge but also explores new possibilities of enhancing the allocation of bandwidth for queue communications. The SARSA agent will take new actions at random with the ϵ -greedy policy defining the probability of choosing random actions. No value change or on-the-fly fine-tuning of ϵ was considered in this solution.

The ϵ -greedy policy matches adequately the inherent need of a Pub/Sub IoT message delivery framework. Random demands from consumers consume Pub/Sub data with different priorities. These demands generate a random volume of data to be transferred from aggregator queues to consumers. The per-queue bandwidth distribution must be dynamically computed among IoT data queues considering the existing constraint (bandwidth limitation) of the available communication channel.

The SARSA Algorithm for Bandwidth Allocation

The end condition for the PSIoTRL bandwidth allocation process is the following:

- ✓ Bandwidth constraint limit is reached; or
- ✓ Current buffers transmission rates corresponding priorities are ($T_1 > T_2 > T_3$); or
- ✓ Maximum number of attempts is reached.

Algorithm 1 PSIoTRL-SARSA Bandwidth Allocation Algorithm Pseudo-code

```

1: procedure PSIoTRL-SARSA( $Q(S_t, A_t, r, S_{t+1}, A_{t+1})$ )           ▶ SARSA states and reward
2:   for each pair ( $Q_t, A_t$ ) do                                   ▶ Initialization
3:     Initialize Q-values -  $Q(S_t, A_t) = 0$                      ▶ Tabula rasa approach
4:   repeat                                                       ▶ Forever
5:     Gets current PSIoTRL buffers state  $S_t$                    ▶ Buffer state is the trigger event
6:     repeat                                                     ▶ Finishes upon terminal condition
7:       Choose action  $A_t$  using the  $\epsilon$ -greedy policy       ▶ Exploration and exploitation
8:       Execute action  $A_t$  on the PSIoTRL system               ▶ T+, T- or do nothing on queues
9:       Get immediate reward  $r_t$ 
10:      Collect new state  $S_{t+1}$ 
11:      Choose new action  $A_{t+1}$  using the  $\epsilon$ -greedy policy
12:      Update Q-value -  $Q(S_t, A_t)$  using SARSA equation 5   ▶ SARSA algorithm
13:    until Terminal condition reached
14:  until forever

```

The algorithm procedure is as follows:

1. The algorithm starts initializing the Q-values in table, $Q(s, a)$;
2. The current state, s is captured;
3. An action a is chosen for the current state using the greedy policy;
4. The agent triggers the action, and observes the immediate reward, r , as well as the new reached state s' ;
5. The Q-value for the state s' is updated using the observed reward and the maximum reward possible for the next state; and
6. Finally for the current cycle, set the state to the new state, and repeat the process until the end condition is reached.

Fig. 17.

— > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

The SARSA agent manages the aggregator's output queues transmission rate according to IoT data demands, IoT data priority, and communication resource constraints (bandwidth limitation). The bandwidth allocation algorithm pseudo-code is presented in Figure 17.

5 Proof of Concept

THE PURPOSE OF THIS PROOF OF CONCEPT IS TO VALIDATE THAT THE AGENT BEHAVIOR ENHANCED THE ALLOCATION OF BANDWIDTH WHEN ONE OR MORE BUFFERS EXCEEDED THE DEFINED BUFFER OCCUPATION LIMIT (50% - AL CONDITION).

WHEN THIS EVENT OCCURS, THE AGGREGATOR DETECTS THE PROBLEM AND SENDS AN ALARM CONTAINING METADATA TO THE ORCHESTRATOR.

AFTER THAT, THE SARSA AGENT ALLOCATES A NEW PERCENTAGE OF BANDWIDTH AMONG THE AGGREGATOR BUFFERS

Fig. 18.

Proof of Concept

FOUR INITIAL BUFFER CONDITIONS WERE USED:

- ONE QUEUE EXCEEDS THE OCCUPATION THRESHOLD (AL, BL, BL);
- TWO QUEUES EXCEED THE OCCUPATION THRESHOLD (AL, AL, BL);
- THREE QUEUES EXCEED THE OCCUPATION THRESHOLD (AL, AL, AL); AND
- ONE QUEUE EXCEEDS THE BUFFER OCCUPATION, AND THE TWO OTHER QUEUES EXCEED THE OCCUPATION THRESHOLD ($+AL, AL, AL$).

Fig. 19.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

The purpose of this proof of concept is to validate that the agent behavior enhanced the allocation of bandwidth when one or more buffers exceeded the defined buffer occupation limit (50% - AL condition). When this event occurs, the aggregator detects the problem and sends an alarm containing metadata to the orchestrator. After that, the SARSA agent allocates a new percentage of bandwidth among the aggregator buffer.

Four initial buffer conditions were used:

- One queue exceeds the occupation threshold (AL, BL, BL);
- Two queues exceed the occupation threshold (AL, AL, BL);
- Three queues exceed the occupation threshold (AL, AL, AL); and
- One queue exceeds the link bandwidth capacity and the two other queues exceed the occupation threshold ($+AL, AL, AL$).

The slide features a blue gradient background on the left with a compass. The title 'Proof of Concept' is centered at the top. Below it, a horizontal line separates the title from the text. The text states: 'THE CONSIDERED PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS ARE THE FOLLOWING:' followed by a bulleted list: '➤ QUEUE (BUFFER) OCCUPATION;', '➤ LINK OCCUPATION; AND', and '➤ PACKET LOSS.'. At the bottom, a dark bar contains the conference name '3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MACHINE LEARNING FOR NETWORKING - MLN 2020 - PARIS - FRANCE', a small image of a city at night, and the date '05/01/2021'.

Proof of Concept

THE CONSIDERED PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS ARE THE FOLLOWING:

- QUEUE (BUFFER) OCCUPATION;
- LINK OCCUPATION; AND
- PACKET LOSS.

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Fig. 20.

- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
The considered performance parameters are the following:
- Queue (buffer) Occupation;
 - Link Occupation; and
 - Packet Loss.

AGGREGATOR			ORCHESTRATOR		
Queues States (B1,B2,B3)	T1i	T2i	T3i	Scenario 1	Scenario 2 (SARSA)
AL,BL,BL					
AL,AL,BL	35%	25%	15%	$T1 = T1i * factor;$	SARSA
AL,AL,AL				$T2 = (100 - T1)/2;$	Module
+AL,BL,BL				$T3 = (100 - T1)/2;$	

† +AL : 120% buffer occupation; dropping packets; factor : 1.15 or 1.25 or 1.50.

Summary of the Proof of Concept Scenarios

SCENARIO 1 – BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION WITH FIXED RULE ALGORITHM

SCENARIO 2 – ENHANCED COMMUNICATIONS WITH SARSA AGENT

Fig. 21.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
 The allocation of bandwidth to the aggregator queues is evaluated in two scenarios. In scenario 1, a predefined simple algorithm is used to allocate the bandwidth. In scenario 2, the SARSA agent does the same task. Figure 21 presents a summary of the evaluation scenarios.

Proof of Concept

THE PARAMETERS AND INITIAL CONDITIONS USED IN SCENARIO 2 ARE THE FOLLOWING:

- SARSA AGENT CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS:
 - EPSILON-GREEDY POLICY ϵ OF 2%;
 - LEARNING RATE α OF 20%; AND
 - DISCOUNT FACTOR γ OF 80%.
- PUB/SUB QUEUE THRESHOLD LIMIT (TRIGGERS AGENT ACTION) = 50%
- AGENT ACTIONS: BANDWIDTH INCREASED OR REDUCED BY 10%
- MAXIMUM NUMBER OF ATTEMPTS = 400

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Fig. 22.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

First of all, it is essential to highlight that this analysis's objective is to verify that the SARSA algorithm enhances bandwidth allocation for an IoT aggregator using specifically a Pub/Sub method to exchange data. In this context, enhanced bandwidth allocation means that the constrained bandwidth resources can be tuned and, consequently, better used for attained QoS performance parameters like delay, jitter, and packet loss.

The evaluated parameters are queue occupation, link occupation and packet loss.

Bandwidth Allocation with SARSA for Buffer Flushing | RESULTS

Fig. 23.

Final Queue Occupation

INICIAL STATE = AL, BL, BL

- ✓ Bandwidth allocation with SARSA performed better than the fixed rule using increments of 15%, 25% and 50% in the buffer flushing bandwidth
- ✓ SARSA algorithm brought all buffers to the final condition BL, BL, BL.
- ✓ The case 1 (50%) was the unique fixed rule option that succeeded to bring the priority queue occupation below the threshold limit.

Fig. 24.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
 For all initial states (*AL, BL, BL*; *AL, AL, BL*; *AL, AL, AL* and *+ AL, BL, BL*) bandwidth allocation with SARSA performed better than the fixed rule using increments of 15%, 25% and 50% in the buffer flushing bandwidth. SARSA algorithm brought all buffers to the final condition *BL, BL, BL*.

- ✓ Bandwidth allocation with SARSA performed better than the fixed rule using increments of 15%, 25% and 50% in the buffer flushing bandwidth.
- ✓ SARSA algorithm brought all buffers to the final condition BL, BL, BL.
- ✓ No fixed rule option succeeded to bring the priority queue occupation below the threshold limit.

Final Queue Occupation

INICIAL STATE = AL, AL, BL

Fig. 25.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
 In Figure 25, the case 1 (50%) was the unique fixed rule option that succeeded to bring one of the queue occupation (queue 3) below the threshold limit.

- ✓ The bandwidth allocation with SARSA performed again better than the fixed rule algorithm.
- ✓ However, while the two priority buffers B1 and B2 are below the limit, buffer B3 (least effort) was set above the limit due to its lower priority.
- ✓ No fixed rule option succeeded to bring the queues occupation below the threshold limit.

Fig. 26.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

In Figure 26, the bandwidth allocation with SARSA performed again better than the fixed rule algorithm. However, while the two priority buffers B1 and B2 are below the limit, buffer B3 (least effort) was set above the limit due to its lower priority.

✓ SARSA algorithm is again the most efficient approach to bring all buffers below the threshold limit.

Final Queue Occupation

INICIAL STATE = +AL, BL, BL

Fig. 27.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**
 Figure 27 corresponds to the evaluation scenario in which we want to observe the behavior of the fixed rule bandwidth allocation and SARSA when buffer *B1* is already experiencing packet loss (above 100% capacity). Figure 27 shows that the SARSA algorithm is again the most efficient approach to bring all buffers below the threshold limit.

Allocated Bandwidth per Queue, Link Occupation and Packet Loss

RESULTS

Fig. 28.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

The algorithm's ability to bring the queue state back to a threshold limit is not an effective performance parameter but demonstrates that the algorithm enhances the usage of the constrained bandwidth resources. For example, keeping the occupation of queues 1 and 2 below 50% would imply having the delay and jitter for the IoT data belonging to the specific Pub/Sub topics within its application's requirements.

- ✓ Two related aspects of link occupation.
- ✓ SARSA allocation of bandwidth per buffer is aligned with buffer priorities.
 - ✓ More bandwidth is allocated to B1 than to B2, and, in turn, B2 gets more bandwidth than B3.
 - ✓ Consistent with the defined buffer priorities
- ✓ The fixed rule method allocates bandwidth to buffer B1 and splits the remaining bandwidth among the other buffers.
- ✓ SARSA succeeds in bringing all buffer occupation levels below the defined threshold and, concomitantly, preserves link occupation below 100%.

Fig. 29.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

In this experimentation, the objective is to use the minimum amount of link bandwidth per buffer to transmit data. Buffer priority should be preserved, and the aimed final condition is to bring all buffers to the *BL* state after bandwidth allocation.

Figure 29 illustrates two related aspects of link occupation. Firstly, it shows that the SARSA allocation of bandwidth per buffer is aligned with buffer priorities. In fact, more bandwidth is allocated to *B1* than to *B2*, and, in turn, *B2* gets more bandwidth than *B3*. This result is fully consistent with the defined buffer priorities. The fixed rule method allocates bandwidth to buffer *B1* and splits the remaining bandwidth among the other buffers.

A second result illustrated in Figure 29 is link occupation. The result indicates that the SARSA algorithm is more efficient than the fixed rule allocation method. SARSA succeeds in bringing all buffer occupation levels below the defined threshold and, concomitantly, preserves link utilization below 100%.

Fig. 30.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:

Packet loss is indicated in Figure 30. The allocation of chunks of bandwidth for IoT data flushing in queues is done proactively once the 50% buffer occupancy threshold is reached. Consequently, no packet loss occurs for three out of four cases considered in the PSIoTRL evaluation (AL, BL, BL; AL, AL, BL and AL, AL, AL). It happens that the buffer flushing bandwidth is adjusted before any packet loss could occur.

The case +AL, BL, BL starts with buffer overloaded and, as such, packet loss does occur since either the fixed rule method or the SARSA algorithm takes some time to allocate bandwidth to the overloaded buffer and fix the problem. As expected, SARSA takes more time to allocate bandwidth due to the learning process inherent to the algorithm and, consequently, presents a more significant packet loss.

6 Final Considerations

- ✓ The PSIoTRL is a solution that addresses the problem of bandwidth allocation in the context of massive IoT data distribution using networks with limited bandwidth resources to aggregators.
- ✓ The SARSA agent in PSIoTRL was able to reconfigure the IoT aggregator queues' flushing transmission rate with these queues reaching the BL (below threshold limit) final condition with less link bandwidth usage.
- ✓ The PSIoTRL demonstrates that a solution based on SARSA is an efficient reinforcement learning approach for enhancing resource (bandwidth) allocation in the Pub/Sub-based massive IoT data exchange context.
- ✓ Future works will address SARSA computation scalability concerning the granularity for allocating new chunks of bandwidth to flush IoT data and adjust the Pub/Sub queue occupancy. The impact of the SARSA configuration parameters (epsilon-greedy policy, learning rate, and discount factor), in the algorithm time response, with a focus on the learning rate, will also be evaluated.

Fig. 31.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT [1]:**

This work has presented a solution to address the problem of network resources allocation in the context of massive IoT data distribution. It has presented a PSIoTRL framework that introduces an architecture that aim to manage the allocation of limited network resources to aggregators.

As highlighted in the simulations, the SARSA agent in PSIoTRL was able to reconfigure the queues' flushing transmission rate efficiently, providing in 100% of the tested cases, that these queues reached the BL (below threshold limit) final condition with less link bandwidth usage. The PSIoTRL demonstrates that a solution based on SARSA is an efficient reinforcement learning approach for enhancing resource (bandwidth) allocation in the Pub/Sub-based massive IoT data exchange context.

Future works will address SARSA computation scalability concerning the granularity for allocating new chunks of bandwidth to flush IoT data and adjust the Pub/Sub queue occupancy. The impact of the SARSA configuration parameters (epsilon-greedy policy, learning rate, and discount factor), in the algorithm time response, with a focus on the learning rate, will also be evaluated.

Thanks Discussion and Questions

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Illustrated slides available at:

- ◆ https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joberto_Martins
- ◆ <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=joberto>
- ◆ <https://unifacs.academia.edu/JobertoMartins>

Fig. 32.

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Fig. 33.

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